

A Historical Analysis of Banditry and Human Security in Some West African Countries in the Sahel Region (2010-2023)

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Abstract:

This discourse examined and analysed the operations of bandits in Peoples Republic of Burkina Faso, the Republics of Mali and Niger and the Federal Republic of Nigeria which are some of the countries in the Sahel region in West Africa. Banditry is widespread in these countries that share borders and easily facilitate the movement of these bandits and other persons of reputable character. Data for this discourse was largely sourced from journal articles, reports from reputable research organizations, and newspapers. Discussion was both descriptive and analytical showing how banditry affects the entire facets of human security. Bandits majorly operated in rural

communities, markets and in some streets in cities, along highways, finding safe havens in large swathes of forests liberally located in these countries. Inadequate security, porous borders, sophisticated weapons and ethnic conflicts were exploited by these bandits to perpetrate their activities. The various governments of these countries have not adequately coped with stemming banditry, hence some communities established vigilante groups for self-defence and to complement occasional security personnel from government. Forceful deprivation of properties, cattle rustling, killing, rape, torture, displacement of victims from their communities and refugees from Nigeria into Niger Republic in particular were largely experienced in these countries.

Keywords: *Historical Analysis, Banditry, Human Security, West Africa and Sabel Region.*

Introduction

The Sahel region in West Africa is located between the Sahara Desert in the North and the Savanna lands in the South. It is largely semiarid region with abundant natural resources in the regional countries namely: Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Chad, The Gambia, Guinea Mauritania, Mali, Niger, Nigeria and Senegal (United Nations Africa Renewal, n.d.). However, this discourse analysed only Burkina Faso, Mali, Niger and Nigeria in the West Africa Sahel region that can be typically described as the hub for banditry. The Liptako-Gourma is the tri-

border zone where Mali (northern section), Burkina Faso and Niger share boundaries. Nigeria and Niger directly share boundaries too.

The Sahel is characterised by large forests and ungoverned spaces that provided a safe haven for extremist groups, militants, bandits, and other criminal groups. For example, the Sambisa, Falgore, and Ajjah forests in Nigeria have been comfort zones for Boko Haram insurgents and bandits who used them as bases and launch-pads for their attacks (Akinyetun, 2023). Similarly, bandits, Jihadists and militants seized and occupied Park W which stretches

across Niger, Burkina Faso and Benin as their base for attacks on their victims (Akinyetun, 2023). Again, this park supposedly was a protected area of a natural forest that was abandoned by the governments aforementioned.

Banditry is a universal phenomenon that has occurred in different climes with different intensity and spread. Large scale and intensive banditry has since 2010 threatened human and all other forms of security in Burkina Faso, Mali, Niger and Nigeria that this part of the West African Sahel has become a source of concern to the global community. In fact, banditry seems insurmountable in this region given its continuity. It is partly for this reason that this discourse is undertaken. Why has banditry lingered in this region from 2010 to 2023? What has given leverage to sustained banditry in this sub-region? What are the effects of banditry on the four states being analysed? How then, can banditry be curtailed for the improvement of all forms of security and development in these countries of West African Sahel region?

These fundamental questions would guide further discussion and analysis of banditry in the West African sub-region. Historical analysis, inheres in explanans (how and why) of an explanandum (a phenomenon or certain events and how situations have come about, of both change and stability) (Smith, 1978). This course, it must be noted is to the past activities of human beings in this sub-region. However, the historian's quest/analysis not only establishes the events of the past (what happened) but also their explanans and meaningful lessons from the analysis, for the present and to guide the future. These enable human beings to understand and solve their problems.

Analysis of Concepts

Two major concepts in this discourse: banditry and human security require some clarification for understanding the trend of this discussion. Firstly, the concept of banditry has been severally defined by scholars with various perspectives from which a concept would be couched for this discourse.

Banditry

Banditry has been defined as a violent organized crime carried out by either a person or group of persons who are outlawed, proscribed and marauding elements called bandits. They move from place to place, town to town (translocational) and across nations (transnational) causing mayhem, destroying properties, farmlands, looting and carrying out heinous crimes such as kidnapping, rape, killings and so on (Okoro, 2022). These crimes are committed with terror inflicting equipment such as machetes, locally fabricated rifles, axes and or modern sophisticated rifles and guns.

Banditry refers to the practice of raiding and attacking victims by members of an armed group, whether or not premeditated, using weapons of offence or defence especially in semi-organized groups for the purpose of overpowering the victim and obtaining loot or achieving some political goals. Such bandits are usually regarded as outlaws and desperate lawless marauders who do not have a definite residence or destination, and they roam around the forest and mountains to avoid being detected or arrested (Abdulyakeen, 2020).

Osasona's approach to the definition of banditry is not direct, rather he discusses the activities, characteristics and operations of bandits. He refers to bandits as a loose collection of various criminal groups involved in kidnap-for-ransom, armed robbery, cattle rustling, rape and other sexual violence, pillage and attacks on traders, farmers and travellers (Osasona, 2023). Given the dynamics of the development of bandits in the post-colonial period, Osasona reiterates that bandits are an assortment of the various criminal groups that among the earlier enumerated crimes also attack gold mineral traders (Osasona, 2023).

From the foregoing, banditry is characterised by lawlessness, use of force and threats on victims, violence, looting among others. It is in this regard that banditry in some West African countries in the Sahel region would be analysed.

Human Security

The activities and operation of bandits in this region being discussed not only challenge human security in this region but also the national security and integrity of the countries of focus. Abdulyakeen, adopted the United Nations Development (UNDP) Programmes 1994 report on Human Development that stressed a people-centered development. In this regard, human security encompassed economic, food, health, environmental, personal, community and political security (Abdulyakeen, 2020). In this discourse, human security would analyse the dynamics and challenges of survival, livelihood and dignity of citizens of the four focused countries of the Sahel region in the seven parameters of the enumerated concerns of UNDP (1994) Development Report. Consequently, banditry has implications for human and societal survival and development, which critically impinges on livelihood and dignity of the people and integrity of the affected countries. Citizens make up a country as such their welfare is prominent and is to be sustained. It is only then that they can strive to maintain the territorial integrity of their country among others.

Banditry in West African Sahel Countries in this Discourse

Burkina Faso shares boundaries with Mali to the north and west, and with Niger to the northeast. Mali shares borders with Niger to the east while Niger shares borders with Nigeria to the south. Trans-border activities (both positive and negative) can take place across these borders and it is in this respect that banditry and human security issues are discussed in this Sahel region. Apart from Nigeria that was colonized by the British, the other three countries were colonized by France. However, the four countries share some cultural and social ties that make trans-border migration difficult. For example, there are Hausa people in both Niger and Nigeria, in fact, kin groups that were separated as a result of boundary delineation by Britain and France, yet this did not deter kinship relations amongst

these groups. Similarly, Fulani and Kanuri peoples are found in Nigeria and Niger. Infact, the Fulani exist in all countries in this discourse and seamlessly move across these borders.

Burkina Faso since independence in 1960 has been challenged by organized and transborder crime, urban and rural banditry (Nsaibia, 2019). The borders between Burkina Faso, Ivory Coast, Ghana and Mali have been virtually controlled by armed bandits. Armed bandits operated in a new dimension from 2018 August when they attacked security personnel on fixed positions and those on patrol such as police men, gendarmeries and custom officials. While these attacks weakened effective security, traders who operated between Burkina Faso, Ivory Coast, Ghana and Mali became vulnerable and suffered huge losses to bandits attacks. The explanan partly is that Burkina Faso and Mali are both landlocked and without outlet to the sea. Abidjan in Ivory Coast (Cote d'Ivoire) provides the sea port used by them. Both countries also have access to the sea through the Dakar (Senegal) port.

Figure 1. Map of Burkina Faso

Bandits therefore operate from Mali and Burkina Faso along these routes to dispossess their victims of their property. The contiguity of these countries make it possible for bandits to spill over to the others even when there is a counter attack on them by military and other security personnel.

Banditry in northern and central Mali witnessed an upsurge in 2016 in addition to attacks and conflicts between Islamist groups, insurgents and government security forces. Bandits routinely targeted public vehicles and buses, animal herders, and traders. Victims reported that government security forces were either unable or unwilling to protect them and rarely investigated the crimes (Human Rights Watch, 2017). The spate of banditry prevented Peul ethnic group cattle herders located south of Douerdza, Mali and traders in central and northern Mali from plying their occupation throughout 2016 (Hoiye, 2017). The severity of bandits attacks was such that many traders could not travel out of Gao, groups of passengers were beaten and robbed after they refused to hand over money while women were raped, even those as old as 50 years.

Figure 2. Map of Mali

Banditry was regular and prevalent in the Timbuktu and Gao regions while few incidents occurred in Kidal and Mopti regions. Swift on their motorcycles, well-armed with various types of rifles, including that of the military, bandits targeted routes on market days. They ordered drivers to stop as they shot in the air to intimidate and robbed passengers of their money, cell phones, and so on. Sometimes, many of these traders were killed and others wounded. Bandits operated in some streets during the day in urban areas in northern Mali. Their impunity was plausible because large swathes of territory in this region lacked the presence of state military personnel or any group that could

provide security to traders and travellers among others.

Banditry became a boom sequel to the onset of the declaration of the independence of Azawad by Tuaregs in northern Mali. This partly leveraged insecurities which spread within Mali and across its borders (Boukhars & Pilgram, 2023). One 35-year old driver from Timbuktu who was robbed three times in 2015, recounted that the bandits left him and his passengers stranded on the road and drove away with his truck, which was his livelihood (Human Rights Watch, 2017). He did not notify the police, having not seen even a patrol of Malian forces all the period of his occupation, on roads to markets.

Banditry in Nigeria, particularly in the North West which comprises seven of the country's thirty-six states features a pathetic narrative that is of great concern. Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto and Zamfara are the seven states of the north-west of Nigeria where banditry is rife.

In 2022, bandits attacked Karfi and Unguwar Tudun Makama communities in the Takai Local Government Area of Kano State. Five persons were killed and Abdulhayatu Ilu, the district head of Karfi was abducted. The bandits came from across the border in Bauchi State (Reporters, 2022). This is a clear evidence of how bandits move from communities or areas where they are well known to operate where or in communities where they would not be easily identified. Somehow, this makes the bandits resilient and not easy to be completely defeated. Troops of 1 Division, Nigerian Army and Operation Whirl Punch neutralized several bandits and rescued scores of victims in Kaduna, Niger and Kano States. In this process countless bandits' hideouts and motorcycles were cleared and destroyed (Alabi, 2023).

In Kano State, bandits' hideout in Dogon Ruwa and Mayan Ruwa in Falgore forest were raided and four bandits were arrested (Alabi, 2023). On April 11, 2023 bandits invaded Gangarbi village, Rano Local Council in Kano State, shot Maskuru Ukaisha on his right leg and Salisu Ibrahim on his left shoulder, both of whom were taken to

Rogo General Hospital while a 60 year old Na'ayya Gangaribi was abducted (Peoples gazette, 2023). Specifically, on July 11, 2023 bandits' location at Sabon Birni, Maidaro, Dogon Dawa, Damari and Saulawa villages, all in Birnin Gwari Local Council of Kaduna State were also raided and same bandits were killed and dislodged (Alabi, 2023). At Fatika on the same day in Kaduna State, the troops had intense fire fight with the bandits and recovered 72 cows, 29 sheep and a motorcycle. On July 15, 2023, a clearance operation at Kuriga and Manini villages in Birniro Gwari Local Council of Kaduna State yielded a positive result. Abducted commuters being taken away to the forest for negotiation of ransom were rescued from the bandits who absconded into the thick forest with gunshot wounds (Alabi, 2023). The 19 rescued abductees were escorted by the troops to their community Udawa to reunite with their family members. At Doka, Maguzawa, Parker and Akote villages all in Chikun and Igabi Local Councils in Kaduna State, bandits were dislodged from their camps. several operational weapons of the bandits such as daneguns, cutlasses and leg chains were recovered during this troops operation on July 17, 2023 (Alabi, 2023). Boderi Isyaku, a notorious bandit and ruthless killer was neutralized in a gun battle with soldiers in Kaduna State. Boderi had for nearly a decade terrorised Kaduna State and neighbouring Niger State but around the Bada general area of Chikun. He lost the battle and some of his members escaped with gunshot injuries (Akhaine, 2024).

Nigerian Army troops also undertook a clearance operation of bandits on August 1, 2023 at Sabon Gida and Sarkin Pawa General Area of Niger State (not in the northwest) in the north-central of Nigeria (Alabi, 2023). Here again, the bandits ran away in disarray. Only one was neutralized and many had gunshot wounds. How would these bandits be located and punished? It is plausible that they regroup and continue to terrorise the communities, particularly those in remote rural areas.

Kaduna, Katsina, Sokoto and Zamfara States in northwestern Nigeria are where banditry is prevalent in Nigeria. Burning of huts, food

stores, cattle rustling, kidnapping, killing, rape, burning and other forms of destruction of farms, forced taxation of farmers among others were features of banditry in these states. Appendix 1 reflects incident of banditry in these states.

Adamawa, Bauchi, Gombe and Taraba States in north eastern Nigeria had more cases of banditry than Borno and Yobe States where terrorist Jihadist groups dominated in the perpetration of crimes similar to those engaged in by bandits. However, bandits, Jihadist/ Islamist insurgent groups differ in their motivation for operation and that distinguishes them.

With audacity, bandits popularly referred to as "Kwanta-Kwanta" (meaning lie down, lie down) from Chad, Niger and Cameroon infiltrated Adamawa State, their neighbour across the porous borders of these countries and Nigeria. Militant bandits known as "Udawa" from Niger Republic who specialised in cattle rustling, being herdsmen too were familiar with the skills needed for this act. Bandits from Chad and Cameroon (these countries are not part of this discourse but contributed to the high incidence of banditry in the northeast) engaged in other forms of robbery and dispossessed people of their property (Project Shelve.com, n.d.). These bandits speak Hausa or Fulfulde language and operated between 10 and 25 persons in a group. They were usually between the ages of 28 and 45 years. Their activities disrupted social activities such as ceremonies and festivals, school attendance, delivery of basic amenities among others (Shalangwa, 2013). This evidence further established kinship (affinity) across Nigeria's borders with linguistic bond of Hausa and Fulfulde languages spoken in the states of the northwest and northeast of Nigeria. Bauchi State witnessed several attacks by bandits that made their Governor, Bala Mohammed bemoan being overwhelmed by banditry in 2023. In Lere district of Tafawa Balewa Local Government Area (LGA), 67 bandits were killed while 29 who were kidnapped, were rescued during a joint security operation by the police, army, local hunters and vigilantes in the state (Leadership? 2023). In another attack bandits killed 20 people and many others were wounded in villages surrounding the Duguri District of Alkaleri

LGA. Aside from loss of lives, communities within the district of Yelwa Duguri had their houses destroyed and their cattle rustled. At Rimi village, 20 people were killed while the attempted attack of Kafin Duguri failed when the villagers defended their village (Bakam, 2022). Vigilante members of “Yan Ba Beli” and “Yan vigilante” who usually jointly trailed bandits in their safe heaven, Burra Forest in Ningi LGA, lost 9 of their members during an operation. They had captured some of the bandits in their hideout in a mountainous area of Ganiji village but, before they left, some bandits came after them and killed one member of “yan Ba Beli” and eight of ‘Yan Vigilante’ (Channels Television, 2023). These bandits are better equipped with sophisticated guns such as AK 47 and ammunitions that are superior to the dane guns used by the local vigilante groups. It is plausible that as long as the bandits resided in the forest and other hideouts around these Bauchi villages they would continue to rob them for their sustenance. Kidnapping for ransom was at its zenith in Ningi LGA where a 20 year old nursing mother and her baby (the wife of a businessman) was kidnapped along with twelve others. Given the frequency of bandits attacks, business activities in this area were crippled. This situation is worrisome that these towns and villages were attacked 16 days after security operatives from the state dealt with some of them. Unrepentantly, the bandits extended their attacks to Sanger, a community in Kwangoro village, abducted one person and later called to ask for ransom. At Billiri Goror village in Lumbu, they kidnapped two residents the same day during the same operation (Premium Times Nigeria, 2023). Gombe and Taraba States also suffered bandits attacks. Amtawalam and Pobawure communities of Billiri LGA were attacked at night during which a 90-year old man was burnt in his house while asleep. Two other younger persons were killed with machetes and three others injured. The bandits also burnt food/farm produce and many villagers fled to neighbouring communities for safety.

Figure 3. Map of Nigeria

In all, troops of the 33 Brigade of the Nigerian Army killed Ya’u the leader of a bandit gang that terrorized residents of Ningi LGA. He used heavy weaponry to intimidate residents of Burra and neighbouring communities and they specialized in kidnapping for ransom. One bandit was also killed along with their leader, while others fled with gunshot wounds. An AK-47 rifle, 14 live rounds of 7.62mm ammunition, a mobile phone and a fetish amulet were recovered by the troops from the bandits (Owolabi, 2023).

The Republic of Niger played two major roles in the banditry saga given its proximity to northwest Nigerian States. Bandits from the Republic of Niger passed through the Rugu forest, attacked the Nigerian States and went back to Niger Republic. It was during such operations that (Batsari, Batsari Local Government Area) (LGA), Safana, Dan Musa, Jibia, Faskari and Sabuwa councils across several LGAs, all in Katsina State were captured by these bandits (United Nations Development Programme, 2006). Oftentimes, these bandits collaborated as bandits from Niger aligned with those from Katsina States to attack any town they desired or targeted. This situation had grave implications for insecurity of both countries. Guidan Roumdji is a suburb of Maradi region in Niger Republic through which smugglers and bandits easily entered Nigeria. Certainly, the inadequacy of security at this border point partly explains this phenomenon. Reiterating this issue, it is obvious that along the border with Niger

Republic are forests and swathes of lands, most of which are not covered by immigration officers and security agents operating under ‘Border Drill’, a patrol team manning the border (Abdussalam et al., 2022). Bandits returned to Niger after attacking Nigerian villages that were at the borders between Nigeria and Niger for their escape.

Tangaza, a border community in Tangaza LGA of Sokoto State had come under attacks by bandits several times. Their victims were taken hostage into a nearby bush and were forced to pay a ransom of N100,000 (one hundred thousand naira) only. This incident explains another dimension of banditry which is the quest for money.

Figure 4. Map of Niger Republic

Another prominent role of the Niger Republic was the provision of shelter or camp where displaced Nigerians were welcome. Villagers who were displaced by bandits in Sabon Birni in Sokoto, Dansadau in Zamfara State, and other communities found refuge in Danga-Zouani, a village in the Maradi region of western Niger Republic. Chadakori is another community in Maradi that welcomed Nigerians displaced by bandits. Infact Chadakori refugee camp was inhabited by the Gobirawa, citizens of Gobir that was one of the seven city states of the 14th century Hausa kingdom. Gobir, had war lords who protected Hausa kingdom from invasion. They have roots in the Niger Republic as well as in Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto and Zamfara. Their Nigerian Liaison contact office is in Sabon-Birini,

Sokoto and shares boundaries with Niger Republic (Africanews, 2022).

Cross border banditry is not a new phenomenon, particularly along the borders between Republic of Niger and Nigeria. That strip linking Maradi to Dogondoutchi had for more than a decade since the early 2010 particularly as a result of external dynamics especially the effects of the war in Libya and the death of Muamar Ghadafti. Since 2011 weapons from Libya transformed the degree and intensity of banditry in the Sahel countries, particularly the countries of focus in this study. Indeed they became complex. These better quality weapons from Libya were acquired by the bandits and used for their swift and precise operations. Other criminal gangs, insurgents and Jihadists also acquired them among others that have fuelled violent extremism, communal conflicts in the Sahel region. From 2010, these gangs became specialized in cattle rustling, kidnapping and targeted killing. From the middle of the decade, Nigerien border: Maradi from 2016, and Tahoua in 2019 became infiltrated by these bandits from Nigeria (Odalonu & Egbogu, 2022). Here again, there are large expanse of woods (forests) along the border from Maradi to Dogondoutchi that shield bandits who reside there and spring surprises on their victims or attack villages and towns in the Niger – Nigeria border. They are equipped with modern and sophisticated arms and ammunitions for their enterprise.

Human Security in Burkina Faso, Mali, Niger and Nigeria: 2010-2023

Human security as a concept emerged as part of the holistic paradigm of human development crafted by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) steered by one time Pakistan Finance Minister Mahbub ul Haq, who was supported by an economist Amartya Sen. Global security concerns on defence, foreign policy objectives with military security was redirected to a broader concern for overall security of individuals from social violence, economic distress and environmental degradation (Kitabu, 2022). This new orientation

therefore included the safety of human beings from threats such as hunger, disease, political instability, and sudden and hurtful disruptions in patterns of daily life. It is in this regard that the discourse on banditry fits in. The following seven core elements of basic needs of human security were enumerated by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) of 1994, namely: economic security, food security, health security, environmental security, personal security, community security and political security. These seven core elements would further guide the analysis in this discourse.

Economic and Food Security

The rural economy of many communities in Southern Kaduna that is sustained by crop and livestock farming, virtually collapsed as a result of banditry (Bisson et al., 2021). Weekly markets were suspended and residents dispossessed. Widespread banditry in Nigeria's north-western, north-central and some states of the north-east deteriorated fast since 2010. The rural areas were largely unprotected by state security personnel, as such attacks were frequent and disruptive to significantly and negatively affect food production in the pre-high spate of banditry that ended in 2009. Rural economies involved creation of job opportunities, reduction of poverty, development of expertise and competence (Human Capital Development) among others, all of which impacted the national economy. Bandits burnt food stores in mud huts, exacted taxes from farmers for the protection of their crops and themselves.

The Republic of Niger has for a long period been challenged by climate and food crises, as well as a young, poor population in need of jobs and some of them sought to arm themselves in response to the bandit attacks along the porous borders with Nigeria (Bisson et al., 2021). In Zamfara State, 13,000 hectares of arable land were destroyed between 2011 when lone banditry commenced in the state to 2018 when it escalated. However, it had become worse in early 2016 when the bandits commenced the attack of another sector of the rural economy, local mining of solid minerals in the state

(Human Rights Watch, 2017). In Niger State, 25 local government areas which were predominantly agrarian lost very many farmers who were killed, chased away from their occupation, thus food and economic security deteriorated (Human Rights Watch, 2017). This feature was also replicated in Mali, Burkina Faso and Niger Republics too. Pastoralism is a serious and intensive economic activity in these countries of study was also affected. It is a livelihood system through which income was derived from livestock production that is dependent on transhumance. There is an avalanche of incidents of security breaches in this occupation. Sharing of resources such as land and water triggered conflicts especially when cattle overgrazed farmers crops or damaged them. Water resources usage was depleted or strained during dry seasons, contributed to the death of cattle and damage of crops where irrigation was not available, particularly in the rural communities where pastoralists and farmers predominated. Small amount of rainfall and climate change deteriorated soil quality that affect both fodder and water for animals and farm crops which they also grazed. In Burkina Faso where pastoralists constitute 40 percent of the workforce and livestock production, power dynamics apart from inadequate resources shaped instability which exploited by bandits for cattle rustling. Pastoralists were politically marginalised to influence the enforcement of national laws that could have granted them access to pastoral corridors/reserved areas for grazing. Pastoral mobility is critical for their sustained livelihoods, essential resilience and adaptation mechanism, needed for economic security.

Commercialization of livestock boost pastoral viability as they are connected to market networks. Mali, Niger and Burkina Faso supplied livestock to Nigeria, Benin, Togo and Ghana. There were regional and global trade networks that stimulated the rise of middlemen who exploited the extant market dynamics to favour intensification of cattle production for meat and milk. Economic and food security consequently are fundamental to human sustenance and security.

Personal and Community Security

The spate of banditry in the Republic of Mali in 2016 was worrisome particularly with regard to personal and community security in northern and central Mali. For example, there were at least 35 attacks on aid agencies in 2016, the vast majority by bandits in the north. At least six vehicles carrying health workers and the sick were robbed and patients forced out of the vehicles in several cases. Certainly this was an infringement on the personal security of these victims which was unwarranted. Again, several thousand civilians were victimized during about 400 incidents of banditry in 2016 (Human Rights Watch, 2017). These were aside from bandits who routinely targeted public vehicles and buses, animal herders and traders. In all these experiences, victims did not receive assistance from government security forces who were either unable or unwilling to protect victims and rarely investigated the crimes.

Hundreds of communities were deserted, and others occupied by bandits in Nigeria's northwest and north central States. From here, they attacked other communities. Niger State alone lost 308 communities in 11 Local Government Areas. Specifically, communities in Rafi, Shiroro, Bosso, Munga, Paikoro, Mariga, Kontagora, Magama, Mashegu, Wushishi and Rijau Local Government areas of the State became ghost communities due to these incessant attacks by bandits (Daily Trust, 2022).

The displacement of people from their communities was widespread in these countries of study and constituted of violations against personal and community security. Maradi region in Niger Republic, along the south-central border with Nigeria had since 2017 been terrorized by bandits from north-western States in Nigeria which resulted in among others, loss of livelihoods as the victims fled to safer communities. In April 2021, the United Nations Office for the coordination of Humanitarian Affairs counted over 25,000 internally displaced Nigerians in the region. They had fled their homes for personal security to towns such as Sarkin Yamma, Gabi, Madarounfa and Maradi. Over 81,000 Nigerians who fled from Katsina,

Zamfara and Sokoto also sought refuge in Niger towns where the Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) were sheltered (Institute For Security Studies, 2022). Nigerian refugees found life in Niger Republic peaceful and relatively comfortable, they received free meals every month at the Chadakori settlement, as well as medical care, including surgeries and maternity services. Sick people who could not be treated in Chadakori settlement were taken to the Gwaramawa Dispensary in Yamai. Their children, over 800 were enrolled into school while a playground was provided for younger children who were not of school age (HumAngle, 2021).

Community policing was adopted in Kaduna State with the launching of Puff Adder I and

II in 2019 and 2021 respectively, in order to address resilient banditry in the north-west of Nigeria. It involved the deployment of mobile police units to vulnerable communities and they worked with community members who among others provided intelligence and reported criminal activities. Most communities established vigilante groups to police their communities but they were overwhelmed by bandits who had better arms and ammunitions and moved in larger numbers for their operations. In 2014, Burkina Faso, self-defense groups such as the Koglweogo ("guardians of the bush" in Mossi language) emerged to defend their communities particularly in the East and Centre-North regions due to very active operations of cattle rustlers gangs and bandits. Security forces (the army and gendarmerie) were ill-equipped to deal with the challenge of banditry that caught the state off guard (Crisis Group, 2020). By 2018, there were 4,500 Koglweogo groups supported by traditional local authorities and traversed the Centre, Plateau-Central, Centre-North, Centre-East and East regions. The Dozo in Ivory Coast, Mali and Burkina Faso asserted themselves as security providers too. In Niger, there were self-defence groups in Tillaberi, Tahoua and Maradi.

Political, Health and Environmental Security

Political security in the four countries being discussed is fragile given the avalanche of terrorists, bandits, militants, Jihadists, farmers and herders disruptive activities that challenge the countries. From the narrative, banditry overwhelmed the government in several sections that strongly challenged territorial integrity. Constant coup d'état, foreign, regional and non-governmental organizations interventions in Burkina Faso, Mali and Niger Republics further destabilized the political stability and development of these countries. For Nigeria, banditry, Jihadists, insurgents and militants have been on the prowl. Political security does not work in isolation but operate together in a strong network of interdependence with health, environmental, personal, economic and other facets of human security.

Environmental security in these countries have been challenged by droughts in Mali, Burkina Faso and Niger that have negatively impacted livelihoods and health. Series of farmers and herders conflicts, the use of land mines and improvised explosive devices by insurgents among others endanger the environment too as well as their accompanied health challenges such as eye and abdominal injuries. At the time these health problems occurred, it was difficult to access health centres or hospitals particularly in the rural areas and people die. There were loss of lives and maiming of human limbs from bandits attacks. In some cases there was absolute neglect leading to loss of lives. In Burkina Faso for example, there was a landslide at Kabonga mining site in October 2018 during which 50 to 100 persons were buried alive and no rescue operation was conducted (Nsaibia, 2019).

Conclusion

Banditry is an organized crime in various forms that range from kidnapping, armed robbery, murder, rape, cattle rustling and the exploitation of natural resources within the environment among others. These forms were found prevalent in the area covered in this discourse.

Large swathes of forests that served as safe havens for bandits to train, strategize their operations, attack and return to base are many in the countries studied. These forests lacked effective presence of government, non-governmental and community security personnel, arms and ammunition and modern equipment for monitoring and containing bandits. With the proliferation of small arms, light weapons and sometimes some more superior arms than those of government security personnel, banditry persisted. Poverty, unemployment, cattle rustling, illegal mining activities unskilled displaced youths without land/cattle and modern skills to start their own businesses sustain banditry resilience. Again, the desire to get rich quickly, irrespective of the risks attached to banditry predisposed youths and made them readily vulnerable to banditry.

Environmental forces in these countries, such as desertification that negatively affect both farmers and herders, reduced land space required for their occupation, inadequate water supply, lack of modern irrigation facilities in the remote communities, drought, climate change, poor soil quality/fertility caused by illegal mining procedures among others exacerbated the involvement in crimes such as banditry. Given the effect of banditry on human security, banditry is a serious challenge to these countries, particularly for their sustained positive intergroup relationship. It is plausible to demotivate banditry by gradually and systematically eliminating/deconstruction of situational opportunities that provide its leverage. There is a need for synergy by these countries to stem banditry and enhance development and human security in all its ramifications.

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Appendix 1

Table 1. Some Incidents of Banditry

S/no	State	Community	Incident	Date	Source
1	Sokoto	Goronyo and Wurno L.G.A.	Bandits attacks that led to death of 7 and several others abducted	December 3, 2023	Nextier, Banditry in Sokoto
		Rabbah L.G.A.	Death of 11 people	9 th November 2023	Daily Analysis December 4, online 2023
		Rabbah L.G.A. Kurya village	= 12 persons burnt alive by bandits at 8.30pm = 3 women were abducted = animals were rusted	26 December 2023	Punch Newspaper online
		Sabon Birni LGA Gatawa community	27 people were abducted = 3 were who hid in a grain store were shot = killed many soldiers, policemen and Civil Defence Officers at a military formation at Dama	30 th August 2021	ThisDay Alive Newspaper online
		Sabon Birni, Gada and Goronyo LGAs communities affected were Gatawa, Dangari & Kurawa	= Bandits killed 13 persons, abducted 73 others	December 28, 2022	Daily Trust Newspaper onlie
		Garin Bature, Garin Faji, Gajet, Lanjegu and Markawa villages were attacked	18 people were killed in 5 villages along Sokoto Road, 12km from Sabon Birni. = Cattle rustling, rape and destruction of houses.	23 May 2019	Human Angle Media online
2	Katsina	Bakori area (LGA)	= Clash between bandits and vigilantes who attacked a village = 50 cows and 30 sheep were stolen = Vigilante (Yankasi) were ambushed by bandits in Yargoje forest and 41 of the vigilante were killed	February 4, 2023	VOA News Africa online
		Dandume Town	= Husband and wife killed = 2 others sustained gunshot injuries, including baby on the mother's back.	Wednesday August 2023	Daily Trust
	Kukar Babangida village in Jibia LGA	20 people kidnapped = An Army patrol vehicle was attacked and two army personnel sustained injuries			

		Maidabino village in Danmusa LGA	Bandits conducted a house-to-house raid, rustled animals, killed one person, kidnapped his wife and went away with his animals	Friday,28	Daily Trust
		Kankara	Over 300 students from Government Science Secondary School students were abducted by bandits	December 15, 2020	ABC News online abcnews.go.com-delive
		Mahuta village of Dandume LGA	80 students of Hizburrahim Islamiyya were abducted by bandits on their way back from Maulud occasion celebrated at Unguwan Alkasim village. They were all rescued by police operations “Puff Adder, Sharan Daji and Vigilante group.	December 19, 2020	ThisDay online. thisdayive.com
		Danbaure village, Funtua LGA	= These same bandits had already kidnapped four persons and rustled 12 cows from Danbaure village, which were recovered as well as the four victims		
3	Kaduna	Kaduna Town	140 students of Bethel Baptist High School were abducted from their boarding rooms	July 5, 2021	CBS News cbsnews.com
		Abuja-Kaduna road flyover near Rido Junction	Attack on travellers in a train. Train was bombed and passengers were also attacked with guns. 10 people were killed and 61 passengers were abducted	8 March, 2022	VOA Africa news
		Afaka, Igabi LGA	30 students from the Federal College of Forestry mechanization, at 11.30p.m. were abducted by bandits	2021	Aljazeera News
		Birin Gwari LGA	Rema Primary School was attacked by bandits at 8.50am and 3 teachers were kidnapped but none of the pupils was abducted.		
4	Zamfara	Jangebe in Talata Mafara LGA	279 school girls from the government Girls Science Secondary School	26 February, 2021	Premium Times Nigeria
		Bungudu district	14 out of 20 students from the Federal University, Gusau were rescued from bandits	26 September 2023	Aljazeera Live online Aljazeera.com
		Wanzamai village	80 boys and girls who went to fetch fire wood were abducted by bandits at 8.00am	April 2023	Vanguard Newspaper online